

D5.2

Dynamic Link to Hazard and Resilience Assessment

Project name

Deployment and Assessment of Predictive modelling, environmentally sustainable and emerging digital technologies and tools for improving the resilience of IWW against Climate change and other extremes

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Table of contents

Quality Control.....	2
Version History	2
Table of contents	4
List of Figures.....	5
List of definitions, abbreviations, and acronyms.....	6
Executive Summary	8
1. Introduction	9
1.1 Project information.....	9
1.2 Purpose of the deliverable.....	9
1.3 Intended audience.....	11
1.4 Structure of the deliverable and its relation to other work packages/deliverables	11
2. Methodology.....	12
3. UAV-based observations.....	14
3.1 UAV-based structural deformation monitoring methodology	14
3.2 Role of UAVs in post-event assessment.....	15
3.3 Limitations	19
4. Satellite-based observations.....	20
4.1 Detection of flooded area.....	20
4.2 Deployment of river and infrastructure monitoring tools	21
5. Risk/impact updating based on UAV and satellite data	27
5.1 Risk and resilience assessment framework in PLOTO.....	27
5.2 Examples of application.....	30
6. Conclusions	36
7. References.....	37

List of Figures

Figure 1: WP5 high-level architecture (source: adopted from D2.2).....	12
Figure 2: Time plan and milestones of T5.5.....	13
Figure 3: Time plan and milestones of T5.6.....	13
Figure 4: UAS mission planning, execution, and data acquisition workflow	14
Figure 5: YOLOv8 network architecture.....	16
Figure 6: Object Detection Model Evaluation. (a) Precision, recall, and mAP@0.5 values over training epochs.	17
Figure 7: Inference results under seasonal and environmental variation in the same monitored area.	18
Figure 8: NDWI for Use Case B (left) and the corresponding extracted geometry (right)	20
Figure 9: A new geometry layer that represents buildings (red) and roads/railways (black) affected by the water	21
Figure 10: Generic architecture of the applications	22
Figure 11: The architecture of the Docker container used to package the three delivered applications.....	24
Figure 12: Flow diagram showing the sequence of activities triggered by the ‘run’ endpoint within the Docker Container	25
Figure 13: A sequence diagram illustrating the activities occurring inside and outside the Docker container when a 'run' command is executed	26
Figure 14: TPDES-based risk and resilience assessment framework: from hazard realization to consequence quantification.....	28
Figure 15: Short-term trans/post-event scenario risk assessment process.	29
Figure 16: Schematic depiction of the satellite-based impact assessment	32
Figure 17: Conceptual results from UAV Mission 1 – Asset (building) in Use Case B with defect detection using multiclass object detection model (YOLOv8) and annotations highlighting corrosion	34
Figure 18: Conceptual results from UAV Mission 2 – Asset (building) in Use Case B with defect detection using multiclass object detection model (YOLOv8) and annotations highlighting corrosion areas.	34
Figure 19: Conceptual illustration of a potential shift in the DS1 fragility curve for seismic hazard.	35

List of definitions, abbreviations, and acronyms

This section provides definitions of abbreviations and acronyms used multiple times throughout this document. Abbreviations that appear only once are defined at their first instance in the text and are not included here.

Abbreviation	Meaning
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
BSI	Bare Soil Index
CV	Computer Vision
CVDD	Computer Vision for Damage Diagnosis
DS	Damage State
DV	Decision Variable
Dx.x	Deliverable x.x
EDP	Engineering Demand Parameter
FTP	File Transfer Protocol
GCS	Ground Control System
IM	Intensity Measure
IoU	Intersection over Union
IWAT	IWW Assessment Tool
IWW	Inland WaterWays
LiDaR	Light Detection and Ranging
mAP	mean Average Precision
MW	Middleware
Mx	Month x
NDVI	Normalized Difference Vegetation Index
NDWI	Normalized Difference Water Index
RAE	Risk Assessment Engine
RAF	Risk Assessment Framework
REST API	Representational State Transfer Application Programming Interface

Abbreviation	Meaning
RGB	Red, Green, and Blue colour
SAM	Segment Anything Model
SES	Stochastic Event Set
STO	Scientific and Technical Objective
TPDES	Total Probability Discrete Event Simulation
Tx.x	Task x.x
UAS	Unmanned Aircraft System
UAV	Unmanned Aerial Vehicle
WP	Work Package
YOLO	You Only Look Once

Executive Summary

The PLOTO project aims to increase the resilience of the Inland WaterWays (IWW) and the connected hinterland infrastructure, thus ensuring reliable network availability under unfavourable conditions, such as extreme weather, accidents, and other kind of hazards. PLOTO's main target is to combine downscaled climate change scenarios (applied to IWW infrastructure) with simulation tools and actual data, to provide the relevant authorities and their operators with an integrated tool able to support more effective management of their infrastructure at strategic and operational levels. The PLOTO integrated platform and its tools will be validated in three case studies in Belgium, Romania, and Hungary.

The aim of this report is to:

- Detail the **Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV)-based structural deformation monitoring methodology**, including the use of multi-rotor vehicles with red, green, and blue colour (RGB), multispectral, and Light Detection and Ranging (LiDaR) sensors for data acquisition, followed by real-time processing to generate and compare 3D point clouds for structural deformation assessment.
- Explain the **role of UAVs in post-event assessment**, specifically the infrastructure flaw detection pipeline utilizing You Only Look Once version 8 (YOLOv8) and Segment Anything Model (SAM) for object detection and segmentation, with a focus on its robust performance across varying environmental conditions.
- Describe **satellite-based observations for detecting flooded areas**, including the integration of Sentinel-2 imagery with derived products and infrastructure data from OpenStreetMap, to identify and map affected buildings, roads, and railways.
- Detail the **deployment of river and infrastructure monitoring tools**, such as the Computer Vision for Damage Diagnosis (CVDD) module for mapping inland water areas and detecting river islets, and YOLO-Boom for identifying defects in industrial buildings, all packaged as Docker containers for enhanced interoperability and resilience.
- Present the **generic architecture of the applications** within the Docker containers, highlighting the input/output mechanisms and the role of Middleware (MW), and elaborate on the functional and integrational tests performed to ensure proper application functionality and communication with external systems like Kafka, GeoServer, and File Transfer Protocol (FTP) server.
- Present the development of workflows and **methodology for linking sensor data** (coming as the main outcome of Work Package 5 (WP5)) into the broader risk model framework established within WP4. This integration will enable a dynamic analysis of the system.

1. Introduction

1.1 Project information

The project entitled “**Deployment and assessment of predictive modelling, environmentally sustainable and emerging digital technologies and tools for improving the resilience of IWW against climate change and other extremes (PLOT0)**” aims at increasing the resilience of the IWW and the connected hinterland infrastructure, especially under adverse conditions, such as extreme weather, accidents and other kinds of hazards. In doing this, downscaled climate change scenarios will be combined with simulation tools and actual data, to provide operators with an integrated tool able to support more effective management of their infrastructure at strategic and operational levels.

PLOT0 project consists in the deployment and assessment of predictive modelling, environmentally sustainable and emerging digital technologies, and tools for improving the resilience of IWW against climate change and other extremes. An integrated tool is set up to allow relevant authorities to improve the efficiency of their infrastructure management. This tool is a combination of downscaled climate change scenarios with simulation tools and actual data. Six complementary avenues will be considered to achieve this integrated tool that will support relevant authorities and their operators for more effective management:

- Measure and use high-resolution modelling data for the assessment of the climatic risk of the selected transport infrastructures and associated expected damages.
- Use existing data from various sources with new types of sensor-generated data (Computer Vision (CV)) to feed the used simulator.
- Utilise tailored weather forecasts (combining seamlessly all available data sources) for specific hot spots, providing real-time early warnings with corresponding impact assessment.
- Develop improved multi-temporal, multi-sensor UAV- and satellite-based observations with robust spectral analysis, CV, and machine learning-based assessment for diverse transport infrastructures.
- Design and implement an integrated resilience assessment platform environment as an innovative planning tool that will permit a quantitative resilience assessment through an end-to-end simulation environment, running “what-if” impact/risk/resilience assessment scenarios. The effects of adaptation measures can be investigated by changing the hazard, exposure, and vulnerability input parameters.
- Design and implement a Common Operational Picture, including an enhanced visualisation interface and an Incident Management System.

The PLOT0 integrated platform and its tools are validated in three case studies in Belgium, Romania, and Hungary.

1.2 Purpose of the deliverable

Deliverable 5.2 (D5.2) “Dynamic link to hazard and resilience assessment” is one of the deliverables of WP5 “Earth Observation, Sensor Data, and Geospatial Services for Increased Resilience of the IWW” and is related to tasks: Task 5.5 (T5.5) “Development of an operational IWW corridor monitoring

procedure” and T5.6 “Linking degradation and damage information into a dynamic hazard and resilience assessment”.

The following description outlines the individual technical tasks conducted within T5.5 and T5.6:

- Development and integration of geospatial monitoring tools designed for the IWW management.
- Implementation of automated modules for detecting river islets and delineating riverbeds using satellite-based water maps.
- Establishment of the methodology and deployment of the infrastructure deformation assessment tools based on UAV-acquired data and 3D point cloud comparison.
- Establishment of workflows to incorporate sensor-derived data (satellite and UAV) into the Risk Assessment Framework (RAF). This focuses on updating the risk model with respect to exposure, vulnerability, and impact, thereby enhancing the accuracy of risk and resilience evaluations and ensuring dynamic analysis.
- Post-event “what-is” flood impact assessment using satellite data. This task involves detecting flooded assets from satellite imagery, matching them to pre-computed flood scenarios, and extracting impact data associated with those scenarios.
- Pre-event vulnerability updating using UAV data. This task involves the establishment of the methodology comprised of conducting UAV missions to capture imagery of assets, comparing data with previous assessments to identify degradation and structural flaws, evaluating the impact of flaws on structural integrity, and updating the asset’s fragility model.

To summarise, D5.2 aims to:

- a. Detail the UAV-based structural deformation monitoring methodology, including the use of multi-rotor vehicles with RGB, multispectral, and LiDaR sensors for data acquisition, followed by real-time processing to generate and compare 3D point clouds for structural deformation assessment.
- b. Explain the role of UAVs in post-event assessment, specifically the infrastructure flaw detection pipeline utilizing YOLOv8 and SAM for object detection and segmentation, with a focus on its robust performance across varying environmental conditions.
- c. Describe satellite-based observations for detecting flooded areas, including the integration of Sentinel-2 imagery with derived products and infrastructure data from OpenStreetMap, to identify and map affected buildings, roads, and railways.
- d. Detail the deployment of river and infrastructure monitoring tools, such as the CVDD module for mapping inland water areas and detecting river islets, and YOLO-Boom for identifying defects in industrial buildings, all packaged as Docker containers for enhanced interoperability and resilience.
- e. Present the generic architecture of the applications within the Docker containers, highlighting the input/output mechanisms and the role of the MW, and elaborate on the functional and integrational tests performed to ensure proper application functionality and communication with external systems like Kafka, GeoServer, and FTP server.
- f. Present the development of workflows for linking sensor data (coming as the main outcome of WP5) into the broader risk model framework established within WP4. This integration will enable a dynamic analysis of the system.

Attainment of the objectives

D5.2 is related to PLOTO Scientific and Technical Objectives (STOs): STO-1 “To investigate and apply various selected solutions (including technical oriented and nature-based solutions) and assess their performance within the inland water ecosystem using a methodology and framework based on specific indicators, action fields, and impact factors” and STO-5: “Improved vulnerability analysis and resilience assessment, including digital winning tools to simulate IWW”. The development of an operational monitoring system for IWW corridors enables real-time degradation monitoring and damage assessment through sensor-based solutions and dynamic data integration. By ensuring seamless monitoring across open and enclosed sections, it supports adaptive risk assessment and decision-making processes, enhancing resilience and incident management capabilities. The methodologies and tools presented represent a significant step towards assessing and quantifying the overall resilience of IWW through a holistic, quantitative approach.

1.3 Intended audience

D5.2 is a public deliverable and thus, it will be openly available to all stakeholders. Those include public authorities, IWW and other hinterland infrastructure owners and operators, researchers, technology providers, as well as decision and policy makers.

The deliverable focuses on presenting IWW end-user needs and requirements related to the design and development of a system that improves the resilience of IWW against climate change and other extreme events.

1.4 Structure of the deliverable and its relation to other work packages/deliverables

D5.2 has been structured as follows:

- Section 1: Describes PLOTO’s aim, as well as this document’s purpose, intended audience, and structure.
- Section 2: Describes the methodology followed in this deliverable.
- Section 3: Describes the methodologies, applications, and limitations of using UAVs for structural deformation monitoring and post-event damage assessment.
- Section 4: Describes the usage of satellite imagery for detecting flooded areas and deploying tools for river and infrastructure monitoring, highlighting data preparation, analysis techniques, and the architecture of the deployed applications.
- Section 5: Describes: a) briefly the risk and resilience assessment framework of PLOTO (from WP4), and b) the methodology for linking sensor data (from WP5) into this broader RAF.
- Section 6: Concludes the deliverable by summarising the main outcomes.

This deliverable primarily presents the findings from WP5 sensor data, building upon its core outcomes. It integrates seamlessly with WP4 modules, particularly those focused on flood hazard modelling and assessment tools. Furthermore, the integration efforts with the PLOTO IWW Assessment Tool (IWAT) platform link this work directly to WP6.

Aspects of this deliverable also connect with other project documentation. For instance, the UAV- and satellite-based observation tools have been previously detailed in D5.1, while the overarching risk and resilience framework is meticulously described in D4.5.

2. Methodology

D5.2 is linked to T5.5 “Development of an operational IWW corridor monitoring procedure” (leader: NTUA, M20-M34) and T5.6 “Linking degradation and damage information into a dynamic hazard and resilience assessment” (leader: SoReCC, M25-M34). In more detail, this work includes several key developments:

- a) the establishment of a framework facilitating seamless information flow from sensors to the risk and resilience assessment system [T5.6],
- b) the development of a robust methodology for the routine detection, characterization, and quantification of degradation phenomena affecting IWW [T5.5],
- c) the integration of satellite and UAV-based remote sensing with advanced data processing techniques, enabling both routine and event-driven monitoring of IWW corridors [T5.5], and
- d) the design and implementation of a modular, operational pipeline [T5.5] which is comprised of the following components:
 - i. UAV-based structural deformation monitoring,
 - ii. automated islet and riverbed mapping, and
 - iii. integration and deployment processes.

Together, these elements form a scalable and flexible operational procedure capable of delivering high-resolution, timely insights into the condition of IWW corridors, supporting both routine monitoring and rapid post-event assessments.

Figure 1 presents the high-level architecture of WP5, where the “Dynamic IWW monitoring” [T5.5] is depicted along with its interconnection with the rest of the WP5 modules. One of the modules, “Post-disaster damage assessment” [T5.4], provides inputs to the T5.5 component. After analysing the received satellite data internally, the system detects water areas and assesses their impact on various infrastructure. The resulting geometries of the affected roads, railways, and buildings are then compiled and delivered via HTTP (Hypertext Transfer Protocol) services to the T5.5 component for further analysis. Furthermore, various disaster scenario definitions are supplied to the assessment tool by T5.3 module and are used to simulate the tool’s output for specific disaster scenarios.

Figure 1: WP5 high-level architecture (source: adopted from D2.2)

To meet the objectives of D5.2, the contributing partners of T5.5 and T5.6 have cooperated closely and communicated via WP5 coordination meetings, ad-hoc meetings, and dedicated bilateral meetings with the end-users. Technical partners worked towards achieving STO-1, STO-5, and the relevant KPIs (Key Performance Indicators).

Figure 2 schematically illustrates the time plan and milestones for the work on T5.5. The methodology implemented for this task consisted of the following steps:

- 1) Methodological framework definition to design a unified approach combining satellite and UAV-based monitoring, focused on damage detection and routine corridor assessment.
- 2) Infrastructure deformation analysis using deep learning, machine learning, photogrammetry, and cloud comparison tools to detect and quantify structural damage.
- 3) Waterway feature extraction to detect riverbeds and islets using deep learning models and automated workflows.
- 4) Module integration and dockerization to package the developed tools for scalable deployment and integration into the IWAT platform for real-time monitoring and user access.

Figure 2: Time plan and milestones of T5.5

Figure 3 schematically illustrates the time plan and milestones for the work on T5.6. The methodology implemented for this task consisted of the following steps:

- 1) Receipt of processed images derived from sensor data (from satellites and UAVs). This step acknowledges the interconnection with the rest of tasks within WP5.
- 2) Exploration of the possible workflows of incorporating the sensor data into the RAF developed within WP4, focusing on updating exposure, vulnerability, and impact.
- 3) Development and integration of an algorithm for flood post-event impact assessment establishing a "dynamic link" between sensor data, the risk assessment, and ultimately, flood hazard and resilience assessments.

Figure 3: Time plan and milestones of T5.6

3. UAV-based observations

3.1 UAV-based structural deformation monitoring methodology

The estimation of the structural deformation is crucial for damage assessment not only for routine monitoring but mostly after an occurrence of a disastrous event. The equipment utilized in the surveys of Use Cases A, B, and C, as well as the specific assets identified by the end users, combined with the methodology employed for both data acquisition and processing, yields prompt and precise results.

The best and recommended practice is to use transportable, light, and flexible equipment that can be used even when the assets and wider area cannot be physically accessed after an event (e.g., due to flooding). The main components of the Ground Control System (GCS) will be used for this case utilizing multi-rotor vehicles combined with RGB, multispectral, and/or LiDaR sensors. Authorized drone pilots can easily obtain the necessary permissions to perform flights in damaged areas and acquire the necessary digital images. To properly survey the assets, both manual and pre-programmed flights will be executed, using the flight plans of the initial documentation that has already been performed for all Use Cases and focusing on the damaged parts of the buildings, infrastructures, and the areas that cannot be accessed. The mapping parameters like the image overlap, camera angle, and flight altitude will be properly adjusted according to the needs and complexity, while the information of the initial flight plans will be used as guidelines for this process.

Figure 4 illustrates the full workflow for mission planning, execution, and data acquisition using Unmanned Aircraft Systems (UASs).

Figure 4: UAS mission planning, execution, and data acquisition workflow

The acquired data will be uploaded from the UAS and then served through various channels, such as Kafka, Geoserver, or Representational State Transfer Application Programming Interface (REST API), for further use and analysis. This way, this data processing can be executed almost in real-time by importing the stored digital images into the IBM (Image Based Modelling) software, e.g., Agisoft Metashape. The Drone Missions & Data Acquisition module has been coupled with the IWAT platform,

capable of providing users with the required functionalities through the UI (User Interface) and making all acquired data available to them. The data processing procedure will focus only on the production of the dense point clouds of the assets to get accurate results in a very short time. The captured images will be aligned, and the sparse point cloud will be edited in the software using the available filters to reduce the inevitable noise and improve the results of this automatic process. Upon successful alignment of the digital images, the initial 3D point cloud or mesh will be used as reference to acquire coordinates for specific points that present no damage or deformation close to the asset. That way the sparse point cloud will be georeferenced to the same coordinate system as the reference 3D point cloud. The next step of the process will be to generate the dense 3D point cloud and re-apply the available filters of the software to edit it and remove the noise.

The proposed methodology will give accurate and fast results leading to the comparison of the 3D point cloud with the reference one after an event. The two-point clouds will be imported into the CloudCompare software (open-source), and a cloud-to-cloud comparison will be performed to estimate the structural deformation of the assets. To further support the results, it is recommended to compute statistical analysis by fitting a distribution on the distances using the scalar fields tool. The mean distance, the standard deviation, and the minimum and maximum values will be available for each case, while the results and the distances will be exported, and a report will be generated. Finally, a more advanced tool will be used for comparison, the qM3C2 plugin of CloudCompare. This plugin offers a unique way to compute signed and robust distances between two-point clouds, and it also provides precision maps.

3.2 Role of UAVs in post-event assessment

The infrastructure flaw detection pipeline developed under the PLOTTO project plays a fundamental role in post-event assessment and was updated for its final implementation stage, utilizing the YOLOv8 object detection architecture in conjunction with the SAM for post-hoc segmentation. This decision was based on extensive experimentation with different model versions and architecture throughout the development process.

YOLOv8 was selected over more recent versions such as YOLOv10 and YOLOv11 after a comparative assessment of their functionalities. While newer iterations introduce architectural changes and performance improvements on certain benchmark datasets, these gains are often coupled with increased training complexity, higher hardware requirements, and a reduced level of transparency in model behaviour. YOLOv10, for example, introduces quantization-aware training and post-processing optimizations targeting edge inference, while YOLOv11 integrates architectural changes with larger receptive fields and deeper convolutional stacks. These modifications, although beneficial in large-scale general-purpose datasets, did not yield consistent advantages when retrained on the project-specific dataset. Additionally, reproducibility and stability concerns were observed in the initial releases of these newer models. YOLOv8, by contrast, offered a stable training workflow, predictable convergence behaviour, and sufficient detection accuracy for the Use Cases, making it the preferred choice for deployment in this phase of the project. Thus, the marginal gains of newer versions did not justify their integration overhead for our domain-specific application.

Figure 5 illustrates the end-to-end pipeline of the YOLOv8 model used, including its anchor-free design and decoupled heads for classification and localization. The figure illustrates the end-to-end pipeline of the YOLOv8 model used in this work. It includes the backbone for feature extraction, neck for feature

aggregation (e.g., PAN (Path Aggregation Network) or FPN (Feature Pyramid Network)), and the detection head for bounding box prediction and class confidence scores.

Figure 5: YOLOv8 network architecture

The YOLOv8 model was ultimately refined using a specialized dataset comprising UAV-acquired imagery, annotated with bounding boxes highlighting construction-related defects. The training emphasized the identification of corrosion, moisture, and debris, particularly in contexts relevant to infrastructures situated near waterways. Performance was evaluated using the standard suite of metrics produced during YOLOv8 training. These include: (i) **precision**, (ii) **recall**, (iii) **mean Average Precision (mAP)** at **Intersection over Union (IoU)** thresholds (mAP@0.5 and mAP@0.5:0.95), and (iv) **loss curves** (classification, localization, and objectness losses). Each of these is defined as follows:

- **Precision** measures the ratio of true positive detections to all positive detections made by the model and reflects the model's ability to avoid false positives.
- **Recall** quantifies the ratio of true positive detections to the total number of ground truth instances and assesses the model's ability to minimize false negatives.
- **mAP@0.5** is computed as the average precision across all classes using an IoU threshold of 0.5. It represents a standard evaluation criterion for object detection tasks and provides a coarse view of detection performance.
- **mAP@0.5:0.95** metric extends this evaluation across IoU thresholds from 0.5 to 0.95 in increments of 0.05, offering a stricter and more informative assessment of localization quality.
- **Loss Functions** tracked during training include:
 - Classification loss measuring the accuracy of predicted class probabilities.
 - Box regression loss capturing the error in predicted bounding box coordinates.
 - Objectness loss indicating the model's confidence in object presence within predicted regions.

Together, these metrics were used to monitor convergence and tune training hyperparameters. The evolution of these performance indicators over time is illustrated in Figure 6a-c, which displays training

metrics, loss components, and the confusion matrix on the validation set. Figure 6a depicts precision, recall, and mAP@0.5 values over training epochs. These curves indicate convergence and stability of detection performance. Figure 6b depicts confusion matrix on the validation set, where class-wise detection performance and error distribution are emphasized. Figure 6c highlights loss components during training, including box loss, classification loss, and objectness loss, where decreasing values confirm learning progress and training stability.

Figure 6: Object Detection Model Evaluation. (a) Precision, recall, and mAP@0.5 values over training epochs.¹

The trained model was further evaluated on a hold-out validation set not used during training. In addition to quantitative evaluation, inference testing was performed on datasets collected from previously unseen locations to assess the model's generalization capacity. These test cases included imagery captured under diverse conditions such as varying altitudes, oblique and nadir camera angles, differing surface materials, and multiple lighting environments including overcast skies, shadowed regions, and high-reflectance surfaces. The objective of these tests was to determine the model's robustness in realistic deployment scenarios and assess its capacity to detect structural flaws that

¹ These curves indicate convergence and stability of detection performance. (b) Confusion matrix on the validation set. Shows class-wise detection performance and error distribution. (c) Loss components during training, including box loss, classification loss, and objectness loss. Decreasing values confirm learning progress and training stability

manifest differently under these conditions. Examples of inference results under such variation are shown in Figure 7a–c. Figure 7a represents a model inference in spring conditions with higher reflectance and ambient illumination, whereas Figure 7b and Figure 7c showcase model inference in winter conditions with overcast lighting and lower contrast.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 7: Inference results under seasonal and environmental variation in the same monitored area. ²

The model maintained stable detection accuracy across these variations, with SAM applied post-inference to refine the bounding boxes into high-resolution segmentation masks. These masks were subsequently processed through a georeferencing pipeline, converting pixel-level detections to real-

² (a) Model inference in spring conditions with higher reflectance and ambient illumination. (b) and (c) Model inference in winter conditions with overcast lighting and lower contrast

world GPS (Global Positioning System) coordinates using UAV metadata, camera intrinsics, and pose estimation from onboard telemetry.

3.3 Limitations

In this section, it is important to mention some restrictions that may arise in this process. Due to weather conditions or official flight restrictions, it is possible that the UAS may not be able to execute a flight right after an occurrence of a hazardous event. The authorised pilots can overcome these obstacles by applying to the appropriate authorities and getting official permission to perform the necessary flights. Moreover, various UAS that offer better wind resistance can be used for the data acquisition process. Otherwise, the flights could be performed in suitable weather. Another challenge for the UAS could be any obstacles close to the assets or high trees that may cover the buildings. These obstructions prevent the aircraft from flying sufficiently close, resulting in gaps in the data, or its misinterpretation, for these asset areas. To mitigate this, ground-based imagery can be acquired using a handheld camera and then integrated with the aerial data to ensure comprehensive coverage.

4. Satellite-based observations

4.1 Detection of flooded area

A multi-sensor synoptic assessment for various disaster scenarios involves developing an infrastructure damage assessment tool tailored to different disaster events. The first step is identifying these events, such as flooding and obstructions in waterways and inland infrastructure caused by debris.

The next phase of analysis is data preparation, which involves integrating satellite imagery (rasters) and infrastructure data (vector shapes). Sentinel-2 images, including bands B02, B03, B04, B8A, and B11, along with derived products like CLDPRB (Cloud Probability mask), Normalized Difference Water Index (NDWI), Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), and Bare Soil Index (BSI), provide critical insights into environmental conditions. Infrastructure data from OpenStreetMap offers geometric representations of roads, buildings, and other structures. GeoPackage file readers and writers support various spatial data operations on these datasets, such as area calculation, buffer zone creation, object merging (union), differentiation, and intersection-based analysis. Additionally, rasterization algorithms are used to convert satellite imagery into vector representations and vice versa, enabling more precise extraction and analysis of geographic features.

The first step in water area detection involves combining indices like NDWI, NDVI, and BSI with the SWIR (Short-Wave Infrared) band, followed by defining a simple ruleset to exclude water and vegetation from the detected area. This produces an initial output. The next step is to extract the polygon bounds of the detected area for further analysis. A threshold is applied to the NDWI to create a binary mask, where values like $NDWI > 0$ indicate water bodies. The geometry of the water area is then derived from the raster using a marching squares algorithm, which extracts contours from the binary water mask. Figure 8 shows the water area of Budapest Freeport after the December 2023 floods, along with the corresponding extracted geometry of the water area.

Figure 8: NDWI for Use Case B (left) and the corresponding extracted geometry (right)

Once the water area is identified and the geometry extracted, the next step is to identify the infrastructure affected by the flooding. This is done by intersecting the geometry of the water area with the geometry of buildings, roads, and railways. Figure 9 depicts affected buildings (red), while roads and railways are depicted in black.

Figure 9: A new geometry layer that represents buildings (red) and roads/railways (black) affected by the water

The output data is provided in universally recognized spatial formats, primarily OGC (Open Geospatial Consortium) GeoPackage and GeoJSON. Within PLOT0 modules integration the latter form of GeoJSON format has been preferred and served via an Application Programming Interface (API), which enables seamless access to endpoints for integration with various applications. The available products include:

- **Buildings:** Shapes representing affected buildings, using OpenStreetMap data as the base dataset.
- **Railways:** Lines representing affected railway infrastructure.
- **Roads:** Lines representing affected road infrastructure.
- **Combined:** A single layer combining all affected infrastructure (buildings, railways, and roads).
- **Detected Floods:** Shapes representing the identified water-covered areas.
- **Metadata:** Aggregated statistics related to other layers, along with general information such as the assessment date.

The flood damage assessment pipeline is dynamic and adaptable, allowing for customization across different regions and timeframes. This flexibility enables the generation of multiple outputs, for example: providing access to flood assessments from various dates when potential flooding events may have occurred. Additionally, the damage assessment tool is provided with disaster scenario definitions, enabling additional static outputs. These outputs are hosted and represented in the same manner as dynamic ones but serve to evaluate the tool's performance in specific disaster scenarios.

4.2 Deployment of river and infrastructure monitoring tools

To support the robust monitoring of IWW and address challenges related to dynamic river environments, dedicated modules were developed for the **automated detection of islets and riverbeds**. These modules build on the foundation of regularly updated water maps produced through advanced deep learning models, which process **Sentinel-2 satellite imagery**. The islet detection module uses a vectorisation pipeline to extract and classify islet features from binary water masks, while the riverbed delineation leverages raster-based edge detection to generate accurate shoreline representations. Together, these tools provide high-resolution, georeferenced outputs in vector and raster formats, thus enabling systematic analysis of IWW changes over time. These modules form a

core component of the data processing chain and are being integrated into the IWAT platform for real-time use and stakeholder access, along with the infrastructure's flaw detection pipeline.

In particular, the **CVDD** module uses state-of-the-art CV techniques to monitor inland water areas and their surroundings. Firstly, the CVDD module operates to map the inland water areas using the WatNet and DeepWaterMap algorithms. Afterwards, CVDD is applied to extract the water areas' shorelines in both raster and vector formats. Finally, detects and classifies the river islets, producing several vector datasets.

The **YOLO-Boom** is an Artificial Intelligence (AI)-powered system leveraging the YOLO object detection framework to identify and highlight defects in industrial buildings. By processing input images, the module detects regions of interest corresponding to structural anomalies such as cracks, corrosion, and other potential defects. Designed for efficiency and accuracy, it enables rapid inspection and assessment, aiding in predictive maintenance and infrastructure monitoring.

Despite their distinct objectives, all these tools have been packaged into Docker containers in a unified manner. This ensures convenient debugging in the early phases of development, enhances interoperability with the rest of the infrastructure, and promotes resilience and agility, contributing to a robust integration. The common approach is that each of these applications expects one or more files as input and generates one or more files as output (Figure 10). All inputs are retrieved by MW, which also expects the corresponding outputs to be sent back. The key differences lie in the types of inputs/outputs and the specific processing performed by each tool.

Figure 10: Generic architecture of the applications

To ensure the proper application functionality, each one is accompanied by well-defined functional tests that cover specific use cases. Below, some common functional tests are described briefly.

- **The Input Image Exists:** All modules expect one or more input files that are used for further processing to generate the corresponding outputs.
- **The Input Image Must Meet a Predefined Minimum Size:** AI model structures typically require specific input dimensions. Therefore, the module's input image should be larger than the model's expected size to prevent information loss.
- **The Model Weights Files Should Exist:** In this module, an inference instance of pre-trained models is utilised for the main processing of the input images, and, as a result, the corresponding model weights, which occur from the training procedure, should be loaded.
- **The Output Image Size Should Be Non-Zero:** This is a fundamental step to verify that the module works as expected. It is not a sufficient condition, but it constitutes, at least, a basic test.

Except for the core of the container, which mainly consists of the corresponding application, an API is implemented to work as a shell around this core, establishing a well-defined communication with the outer world. This approach appears to offer several advantages:

- **Security:** The application is fully isolated from the external world and only specific functionalities are provided, without exposing details about the software itself.
- **Monitoring:** Having dedicated endpoints for testing the application or for retrieving useful information of the running instance, the monitoring becomes easier in both testing and production.
- **Flexibility-Interoperability:** The application can be easily integrated with other systems without modifying the container.
- **Scalability:** Many instances of the container can be executed independently, serving multiple users at the same time.
- **Error Handling:** Errors and log files can be easily exposed by a specific endpoint, facilitating better error handling.

According to the Docker container architecture presented in Figure 11, the application itself has direct access only to the input/output folders. There is no other type of communication with the outer world. Even the arrow from the 'Organizer' to the application is one-directional, depicting the triggering actions described below. The 'Organizer' is the core component of the API section since it orchestrates all the actions needed for the smooth operation of the container. The 'Kafka topic subscriber' module enables the subscription to the predefined Kafka topic and undertakes the task of polling this topic to receive new messages. With the arrival of such a message, this module unpacks it and delivers the contents to the 'Organizer'. The 'GeoServer/FTP server connector' module has the capability to establish connections to GeoServer and the FTP server for file exchange when the corresponding paths are known. Finally, the endpoints of the API are organised in three main groups: (i) the Functional tests, (ii) the Integrational tests, and (iii) the Executional endpoints to route the relevant requests in a more convenient way.

Figure 11: The architecture of the Docker container used to package the three delivered applications

When a 'run' command reaches the execution endpoints, it is first collected by the 'Organizer'. The integrational tests are executed to ensure proper communication with 'Kafka', GeoServer, and FTP server. After passing these tests, the 'Organizer' enables the 'Kafka topic subscriber' to subscribe to the relevant topic, preparing to receive the next Kafka message. Once received, the message is processed to extract the path of the newly uploaded file/image on the GeoServer or FTP server. Using this information, the 'Organizer' triggers the 'GeoServer/FTP server Connector' to establish a connection, download the image, and store it in the local input folder. The functional tests are now executed to ensure that everything is ready for triggering the application. At this stage, the application is launched and begins processing the image to generate the desired output. Finally, the 'Organizer' calls the 'GeoServer/FTP server Connector' once more to transmit the output back to the MW. This procedure is illustrated in the flow diagram shown in Figure 12.

Figure 12: Flow diagram showing the sequence of activities triggered by the 'run' endpoint within the Docker Container

The sequence diagram of Figure 13 offers a more detailed overview of the processes inside and outside the Docker container when the 'run' command is executed. It illustrates how the sub-modules interact under the supervision of the 'Organizer' to maintain a logical sequence of events, ensure the correct execution of tasks, and verify workflow integrity, ultimately leading to a robust execution of the entire module. Additionally, the diagram highlights the key communication flows between components, showcasing how data is exchanged and processed at different stages. Furthermore, it provides insight into potential failure handling mechanisms, ensuring resilience and reliability in execution.

The integrational tests are designed to guarantee a suitable connection with the rest of the infrastructure that will facilitate the final working version of the modules. As with the functional tests, most of the integrational tests are common to all three modules. Some of them are described below:

- **Kafka Connection Verification:** The 'Kafka topic subscriber' module is triggered by the 'Organizer' to test the connection with the Kafka broker. The former sends a request to the broker and, according to the response, it decides if the connection works.
- **API Response Validation:** Received Kafka message typically includes a path pointing to a specific file or image. Using this path, an API GET call is initiated to fetch the file. Additionally, each application should send its output back to MW via an API POST request. To confirm both directions, the 'GeoServer/FTP server Connector' sends test GET/POST requests, triggered by the test case, to validate proper communication with the corresponding API endpoints.

Additional integration tests exist, but they are more targeted toward specific subsets of the three applications. For this reason, they are not explained further in this report. However, the aforementioned tests provide a clear overview of the functionality of these tests.

Figure 13: A sequence diagram illustrating the activities occurring inside and outside the Docker container when a 'run' command is executed

5. Risk/impact updating based on UAV and satellite data

5.1 Risk and resilience assessment framework in PLOT0

This sub-chapter provides a brief description of the RAF incorporated within PLOT0, which is an outcome of WP4. A more detailed explanation of the framework can be found in PLOT0's D4.5.

5.1.1. Framework brief overview

A general **risk and resilience assessment framework** (Vamvatsikos and Chatzidaki 2022; Chatzidaki 2024) has been integrated into PLOT0, aimed at protecting IWW and their connected hinterland infrastructure from a wide range of natural hazards. In line with recent advancements, this framework shifts from single-hazard assessments to **multi-hazard assessments** (Argyroudis et al. 2020) and from evaluating individual assets (e.g., FEMA 2012) or clusters of assets (Silva et al. 2020) to examining **interconnected systems**. By modelling interconnections between assets, the framework captures how local damage propagates through the broader network, ultimately guiding more resilient planning and response strategies.

At its core, the framework employs a discrete-event, Monte Carlo–based approach known as Total Probability Discrete Event Simulation (TPDES) approach, largely based on the Cornell-Krawinkler framework (Cornell and Krawinkler 2000). This approach incorporates:

1. **Stochastic Event Set (SES) Generation:** For each hazard (e.g., earthquake, flood, wind), a catalogue of potential events (ruptures, rainfall scenarios, storms) is synthesized. Each event is characterized by one or more spatially correlated Intensity Measure (IM) fields, which define how hazard intensity varies across the study area.
2. **Exposure Model Mapping:** All assets at risk (e.g., canals, buildings, port cranes) are mapped into a geospatial “Exposure Model,” which describes their location, structural characteristics, and functional roles within the network.
3. **Engineering Demand Parameters (EDPs):** For a given IM realization, each asset’s structural or functional response is estimated in terms of one or more EDPs (e.g., story drift for buildings).
4. **Damage State (DS) Assignment:** Probabilistic fragility functions convert EDPs into discrete DSs (e.g., “slight,” “moderate,” “extensive,” or “complete” damage), accounting for uncertainties in how structures behave.
5. **Decision Variables (DVs) and Consequences:** Finally, each DS is translated into one or more DVs—such as repair/restoration cost, downtime, or network-level service disruption.

The framework supports distinct types of assessments, which can be categorized as follows:

- Probabilistic Assessments:
 - Long-term pre-event analyses
 - Short-term trans/post-event analyses
- Event-Specific Impact Analyses:
 - "What-if" scenario evaluation (for hypothetical events)
 - "What-is" assessment (for actual, observed events)

5.1.2. Long-term pre-event assessment

Long-term assessments generate annualized statistics of potential consequences—such as damage, financial loss, and recovery time—to support planning and preparedness. Using the TPDES approach, the framework performs large-scale Monte Carlo analyses: for each simulated hazard realization (i.e., IM), it propagates uncertainty through the EDPs and subsequent DSs to derive the DVs (e.g., repair costs or downtime). By summing over all IM → EDP → DS → DV “chains,” each weighted by its joint probability, the framework computes the Mean Annual Frequency of every DV. Aggregating these outcomes across many realizations yields loss curves, loss maps, and other annualized risk metrics that directly inform long-term investment decisions and resilience-enhancement strategies. The overall process—from hazard generation through consequence quantification—is depicted in Figure 14.

Figure 14: TPDES-based risk and resilience assessment framework: from hazard realization to consequence quantification³

5.1.3. Short-term trans/post-event assessment

Traditional risk assessment approaches primarily focus on long-term, pre-event analyses, emphasizing annualized estimates of damage, economic loss, and recovery time. However, the increasing availability of affordable and deployable sensors now enables short-term risk and resilience assessments—during the occurrence of an event (e.g., ongoing flood) or immediately after (e.g., earthquake). These sensors enable more frequent and even continuous monitoring, expanding the capabilities for tracking changes in hazards and asset conditions. In general, sensors relevant to dynamic risk assessment can be categorized by the type of information they provide :

- **Hazard sensors:** Instruments such as seismographs and weather stations that provide actual values of the hazard IMs experienced at specific locations.
- **Response sensors:** Devices like accelerometers and strain gauges that monitor the real-time structural response of assets to environmental stressors.

³ Adopted from Vamvatsikos and Chatzidaki, 2022

- **Impact sensors:** Visual sensors, such as cameras (with or without CV algorithms) or other inspection technologies assess visible damage or degradation. Data from these sensors are vital for improving estimations of 'Impact,' particularly in the immediate aftermath of an event, and can also be used to validate and refine fragility models over time.

By comparing near-real time sensor readings against the pre-computed SES-to-DV scenarios, the framework filters out any combinations of IM/EDP/DS that are inconsistent with observed data, yielding a reduced “scenario set”. Within that subset, probabilities are re-weighted to reflect which scenarios remain viable given the sensor inputs. In turn, this allows near-instant estimates of DVs (e.g., actual repair costs) conditioned on what has been observed avoiding repeated time-consuming analyses. This filtering of inconsistent SES, asset response, and impact scenarios reduces risk assessment uncertainty. The extraction of all DS, EDP, and IM scenarios which are compatible with the observations is depicted in Figure 15.

Figure 15: Short-term trans/post-event scenario risk assessment process.⁴

5.1.4. “What-is” event impact assessment

In the risk-and-resilience assessment, a “what-is” analysis refers to any situation in which one component of the RAF chain is treated as known. For example, as in PLOTO's case, this could be the realized spatial extent of a hazard in real time extracted from advanced earth-observation satellites, UAV imagery, and automated techniques (e.g., CV and machine-learning algorithms).

Even knowing a single RAF parameter is sufficient to consider a triggered “what-is” event assessment. Such observed data may be utilized to bypass other RAF components and provide further assessment results. For example, in PLOTO, knowing the actual spatial extent of a hazard allows for the immediate identification of impacted buildings or infrastructure. PLOTO isn't limited to just this initial identification. It actively queries its extensive library of pre-computed scenarios to provide even more impact data and develop a comprehensive risk and resilience picture. This means the estimated consequences, expressed through DVs, for the observed event are directly derived from the pre-computed consequences linked to similar identified scenarios. This strategy enables a rapid generation

⁴ The bolded/non-blurred scenarios are those that best match the information provided by the sensors (adapted from Vamvatsikos and Chatzidaki 2022)

of consequence estimates, offering crucial situational awareness to decision-makers immediately following an event.

Having provided the general description of the RAF in PLOTTO and the importance of the sensors data, the next section presents detailed applications of WP5 sensor outputs within specific parts of the proposed RAF.

5.2 Examples of application

Risk assessment parameters are not static. They are subject to change due to evolving hazards (e.g., climate change) and alterations in the IWW itself, including damage from disaster events and the effects of intervention (or lack thereof) regarding infrastructure degradation.

To ensure that the risk assessment remains current and reflects the actual state of IWW infrastructure, the integration of sensor-derived data obtained within WP5 into the RAF developed within WP4 has been explored. Specifically, the exploration has focused on establishing procedures for linking sensor data from two types of applications: satellites and UAVs. This exploration of the "linking" process specifically investigates how sensor data can be used to inform and update the risk model with respect to three key areas:

- **Exposure:** Updating information on the location, extent, and characteristics of assets at risk.
- **Vulnerability:** Refining assessments of the susceptibility of assets to damage based on their current condition.
- **Impact:** Improving estimations of the potential consequences of hazard events, considering direct damage.

By dynamically incorporating sensor data, the project moves beyond static risk assessments, enabling a more accurate and responsive approach to risk management. The following sections present two application examples developed within the project: first, an example of impact online-updating based on satellite data, and second, an example of vulnerability offline-updating based on conducted UAV missions.

5.2.1. Example 1: Satellite flood “what-is” post-event impact updating

This section details a methodology developed within PLOTTO for flood “what-is” post-event impact assessment using satellite data. This aligns with the corresponding PLOTTO assessment type discussed in Section 5.1.4. Specifically, it explores how satellite-derived flood detection can be integrated with pre-computed inundation scenarios to estimate flood impact on assets. While satellite imagery effectively identifies flooded buildings, it typically lacks the crucial information on flood height required for accurate damage and loss assessment. The PLOTTO approach bridges this gap by leveraging pre-computed flood scenarios that contain both flood height and impact data, enabling a more comprehensive post-event analysis. By associating detected flooded buildings with pre-computed scenarios, reliable estimates of flood height and corresponding economic impact can be derived. This methodology enables near real-time loss assessment without requiring direct flood height measurements.

The methodology is depicted in Figure 16 and involves identifying flooded assets from satellite imagery, matching these assets to the most similar pre-computed flood scenario, and extracting impact data (e.g., economic losses, number of affected assets) associated with that scenario to provide an impact assessment. In more detail:

1. **Flood Detection (Satellite-Derived):** Post-event satellite imagery detects and lists flooded assets (as presented in Section 4.1). The output is a binary classification: flooded or non-flooded assets.
2. **Pre-computed Flood Scenarios:** A library of flood scenarios exists, each represented as a time-series dataset. These scenarios include flood propagation data and associated flood losses. The scenarios are based on overtopping and inundation analyses rather than general precipitation-based flooding.
3. **Scenario Matching:** The detected flooded buildings are compared to the pre-computed inundation scenarios. If a significant overlap exists between the detected flood-affected area and a pre-computed scenario, this scenario is selected as the closest match. The underlying assumption is that if the majority of detected flooded buildings are within a specific pre-computed flood extent, then the corresponding scenario is a reasonable approximation of the actual event.
4. **Flood Height Estimation:** Once the nearest neighbour scenario is identified, the flood height of the detected asset is assumed to be the flood height of the same asset from the selected pre-computed scenario.
5. **Loss Estimation:** Once the flood height is identified, pre-computed direct loss data corresponding to the matched scenario can be applied.

Justification for this approach. The studied area functions as a “basin,” meaning water accumulation patterns in the pre-computed scenarios can be reliably assumed to remain valid for flood height approximation.

Limitations. The accuracy of this approach depends on the assumption that the pre-computed scenarios adequately represent the actual flood event. If the detected flooded buildings are not located within a pre-computed floodplain, loss assessment using this method cannot be conducted due to missing flood height data. In such cases, only the information regarding binary flood status (flooded/non-flooded) (and potentially its usage type) can be reported.

Implementation. The flood detection process occurs online (real-time processing). The pre-computed scenarios are accessed from a structured database to ensure rapid scenario matching and impact estimation. The system’s output is either full flood impact data (if a match is found) or a basic flooded/non-flooded classification.

Post-event impact assessment Utilization of pre-computed flood scenarios

Satellite detected flooded assets

Scenario matching (if applicable)

Output: Impact

Figure 16: Schematic depiction of the satellite-based impact assessment⁵

⁵ The process involves identifying flooded assets from satellite imagery, matching these assets to the most similar pre-computed flood scenario, and extracting impact data (e.g., economic losses, number of affected assets) associated with that scenario to provide an impact assessment

5.2.2. Example 2: UAV pre-event vulnerability updating

This section explores the potential of utilizing UAV readings within the risk and resilience framework of exposed assets to natural hazards. This discussion focuses on the pre-event phase of risk assessment, where UAV-derived data can be particularly valuable for updating assets vulnerability.

Risk assessments typically capture a static condition (a snapshot) of assets at a specific time. Because these conditions can change over time, periodic updates to reflect changes in vulnerability are necessary to maintain the validity and utility of risk assessments. These updates should be conducted at regular intervals, such as every three to five years, or as otherwise specified by project requirements. UAVs offer a powerful tool for efficiently capturing even subtle changes, particularly regarding structural flaws and degradation that might otherwise go unnoticed.

5.2.2.1. Workflow for updating vulnerability

To effectively integrate UAV findings into the vulnerability updating, the following workflow is proposed:

1. **UAV Data Acquisition:** Conduct targeted UAV missions to capture high-resolution imagery of the asset.
2. **Comparative Analysis:** Compare newly acquired data with previous assessments (including baseline data if available) to identify areas of degradation and specific structural flaws (e.g., corrosion).
3. **Structural Evaluation:** Evaluate the detected flaws in terms of their impact on structural integrity and potential degradation patterns. This involves translating visual observations into quantifiable engineering assessments, often through the application of established engineering principles, analytical tools, and expert judgment.
4. **Fragility Model Update:** Based on the identified flaws and their structural implications, update the relevant parameters of the asset's fragility model. This might involve adjusting fragility curves to reflect the increased vulnerability due to detected degradation.
5. **Reporting:** Generate a concise report summarizing the updated vulnerability state of the asset, including details of the detected flaws, their impact on structural integrity, and the resulting changes to the fragility model.

5.2.2.2. Conceptual example: Warehouse B7, Port of Budapest

This conceptual example demonstrates how UAV observations can inform the pre-event vulnerability assessment indicatively of Warehouse B7, a grain-storage warehouse in the Port of Budapest (identified in the exposure modelling undertaken in T4.2). The warehouse is constructed in 1928 of reinforced concrete with load-bearing walls and is equivalent to 10 stories high (excluding a 3-story roof tower). Although the building design did include seismic considerations via the so-called "Conventional Static Calculus" which was used during the construction period in Hungary (Csaba and Gobesz 2013) (making it more than a "no-code" approach), it critically lacked ductility requirements. Thus, the asset's initial fragility curve is based on the "CR_LWALL-DUL_H10" classification from the ESRM20 framework (Crowley et al. 2021).

Conceptual Flaw Detection and Vulnerability Update:

UAV Mission 1: Initial UAV imagery (Figure 17) reveals potential minor corrosion on exposed elements. YOLOv8 is used to detect potential corrosion based on visual cues such as discoloration and surface texture. The highlighted areas indicate regions of interest identified by the model. It is important to

note that this automated detection is subject to uncertainty, and further investigation is required to validate these findings.

Figure 17: Conceptual results from UAV Mission 1 – Asset (building) in Use Case B with defect detection using multiclass object detection model (YOLOv8) and annotations highlighting corrosion

UAV Mission 2 (e.g., 3 years later): Subsequent UAV data reveals a notable increase in the extent and severity of corrosion in comparison with UAV Mission 1, suggesting a worsening condition. Representative results of such UAV mission are indicatively depicted in Figure 18. This observed degradation translates to potential decrease in the structural capacity of the warehouse.

Figure 18: Conceptual results from UAV Mission 2 – Asset (building) in Use Case B with defect detection using multiclass object detection model (YOLOv8) and annotations highlighting corrosion areas.⁶

Vulnerability Update: Figure 19 illustrates a conceptual shift in the fragility curve for DS1: state of slight damage. This shift is not a direct result of the detection model (YOLOv8). Instead, it represents

⁶ The increased number and extent of these areas, in comparison with the results of UAV Mission 1, suggest a potential worsening of the asset's condition

how the qualitative information gained from the UAV missions can inform expert judgment regarding the asset's vulnerability. The increased corrosion observed in UAV Mission 2 suggests a potential decrease in the asset's structural capacity. This observation would likely prompt a structural engineer to conduct a more detailed assessment, potentially including on-site inspections and material testing. The results of this assessment could then be used to quantify the impact of the corrosion and update the fragility curves accordingly. For instance, Figure 19 shows that at a Peak Ground Acceleration (PGA) of 0.3g, the probability of exceeding DS1 increased from 17.3% to 23.1% due to building deterioration between UAV Mission 1 and UAV Mission 2. The conceptual shift shown in Figure 19 illustrates how the UAV data can highlight potential vulnerabilities and initiate a process of expert evaluation and model refinement.

Fragility Functions for Damage State 1: Updating of Fragility with UAV Flaw Detection

Figure 19: Conceptual illustration of a potential shift in the DS1 fragility curve for seismic hazard.⁷

This example demonstrates how UAVs can provide valuable data for triggering further investigation and informing expert judgment in the case of pre-event vulnerability assessments. The ability to detect and monitor potential structural flaws allows for a more dynamic and accurate representation of risk, ultimately leading to better-informed risk management decisions.

⁷ The shift to the left represents an increased probability of exceeding DS1 at lower intensity levels, reflecting the potential impact of the observed corrosion. This shift is illustrative and does not represent a quantified update to the fragility model. It serves to highlight the potential impact of the observed degradation on the asset's vulnerability and the need for further expert evaluation.

6. Conclusions

This report constitutes the deliverable of WP5 denoted as D5.2, "Dynamic link to hazard and resilience assessment", and is related to T5.5 "Development of an operational IWW corridor monitoring procedure" and T5.6 "Linking degradation and damage information into a dynamic hazard and resilience assessment". It details the successful development and operationalization of advanced monitoring procedures for IWW corridors and the hinterland infrastructure.

UAV-based methodologies now enable prompt and precise structural deformation assessment through 3D point cloud comparison and effective infrastructure flaw detection using AI-driven image analysis (YOLOv8 and SAM). These tools directly support pre-event vulnerability updates by identifying and monitoring asset degradation.

Satellite-based techniques provide rapid post-event flood impact assessments by mapping inundated areas and affected infrastructure using Sentinel-2 imagery. Additionally, automated systems monitor dynamic river features such as islets and riverbeds. The robust Dockerized deployment of these satellite-data processing tools ensures their scalability and integration into the IWAT platform for operational use.

D5.2 is crucial for achieving a dynamic risk management approach for IWW infrastructure. Addressing the limitations of static risk assessments, it integrates satellite and UAV data into the WP4 risk model, updating vulnerability and impact assessments. Two key examples demonstrate this approach. First, online post-event flood impact is rapidly assessed using satellite-derived flood detection matched with pre-computed inundation scenarios, enabling near real-time impact (loss) estimation. Second, offline pre-event vulnerability is updated via UAV missions, detecting and monitoring infrastructure degradation, informing expert evaluations, and refining asset fragility models. These dynamic updates, driven by sensor data, are essential for effective IWW risk management, ensuring assessments reflect current conditions and enabling proactive interventions to enhance resilience. D5.2's integration of sensor data and dynamic analysis is vital for improved hazard and resilience assessments, ultimately supporting the PLOTTO project's goals.

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